

Turmeric Massage Essential Oil Production for Business

GERALDINE DC. CAWAGAS, MBA

Abstract:- This study discovered that a variety of medical conditions can be managed or overall health can be improved with massage therapy using the product name *Curcuma Longa - Turmeric Massage Essential Oil*. This study's findings suggest that it may be helpful for fatigue, body pain, and muscle pain. This study used a descriptive survey method that involved survey questionnaires and an informal interview with the respondents. The study's findings show that this product is affordable, suitable for use as massage oil, and effective in the management of muscle discomfort issues. It may also present excellent business and revenue prospects.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, turmeric has been used in Chinese and Indian Ayurvedic medicine to treat arthritis since turmeric's active components are known to block inflammatory cytokines and enzymes. That's why it's known as one of the best [essential oils for arthritis](#) around.

Studies have shown turmeric's ability to help reduce pain, inflammation and stiffness related to [rheumatoid arthritis](#) and osteoarthritis. One study published in the *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* evaluated the anti-arthritis effects of turmeric essential oil and found that crude turmeric essential oil given orally at a dose that would correspond to 5,000 milligrams per day in humans had a modest anti-inflammatory effect on the joints of animal subjects.

What is turmeric exactly? Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the ginger family (*Zingiberaceae*). The turmeric plant grows to a height of about three feet and has yellow flowers. The root is bright orange with a thin brownish skin. Native to southern India and Indonesia, turmeric is cultivated on the mainland and in the islands of the Indian Ocean.

Turmeric essential oil is derived from the plant's tuberos rhizomes, or underground roots. The Turmeric essential oil is considered to be a strong relaxant and balancer, and studies have shown it can help fight against two extremely common mood disorders, depression and anxiety.

As an effective [essential oil for anxiety](#) and depression, it may improve mood and positive feelings. the solvent [hexane](#). You ideally want a turmeric oil that is CO₂-extracted. Turmeric essential oil is yellow in color and has an interesting scent that can be described as sweet and woody with notes of spice.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted to create massage essential oil that will be labeled as *Curcuma Longa - Turmeric Massage Essential Oil*. Also, the researchers wanted to learn more about the massage oil production process and how the respondents rated it in terms of look, scent, texture, and effect using sensation test. Specifically, it sought to answers the following questions:

A. *How may the profile of the respondents be described in terms of:*

- Age;
- Sex;
- Nature of Work; and
- Muscle Pain Encounter.

B. *Describe the preference and experience of the respondents in terms of:*

- Look;
- Scent;
- Texture; and
- Effect:
- ✓ Body Pain;
- ✓ Muscle Pain; and
- ✓ Skin.

C. *Problems encountered by the respondents in using the product.*

Additionally, this study will compile the advice and suggestions of 100 respondents based on their interactions with the product. Additionally, it intends to set guidelines for the College of Management and Business Technology at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology to produce new products that have the potential to be profitable inventions. The researcher's institution's production and extension initiatives will be used to communicate this concept to the public.

III. METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey method was employed by the researcher. The objective of this product development will be to create a new product through experimental research that will appeal to the general community. It was also used to record the results of measurements and observations. The sample product will be put to the test by the researchers to see what the respondents prefer in terms of appearance, fragrance, texture, and impact. For the sensory evaluation of the final product, a nine-point hedonic scale will be used in the questionnaire. Hedonic scales are well tried and tested in consumer research for capturing liking data (Stone and Sidel, 1985). Figure 1. shows a typical example of a nine-point hedonic scale, a version regularly used with consumers in preference mapping studies to capture liking scores.

Table 1: Nine-Point Hedonic Scale with Verbal Anchors

Dislike Extremely	Dislike Very Much	Dislike Moderately	Dislike Slightly	Neither Like nor Dislike	Like Slightly	Like Moderately	Like Very Much	Like Extremely

A. *Materials*

The ingredient used includes the following:

➤ *Turmeric Roots:*

Fig. 1: Turmeric Roots

➤ *Coconut Oil*

Fig. 2: Coconut Oil

➤ *Menthol Crystals:*

Fig. 3: Menthol Crystals

B. PROCEDURES:

- Step 1. Prepare all the necessary ingredients needed.
- Step 2 .With clean water, wash the turmeric roots.
- Step 3. Rub the turmeric roots in a grater that will form a smooth paste.
- Step 4. Collect at least 1-2 tablespoons of turmeric paste.
- Step 5.Mix turmeric paste with 50 ml of coconut oil.
- Step 6. Stir it well and let it stay in a container for about 20-30 minutes and let it soak.
- Step 7. In a clean container, add the mixed turmeric paste, and coconut oil.
- Step 8. Take a pan, fill it up with water and put the container that contains the mixture of turmeric paste and coconut oil.
- Step 9. Heat for a minute with low flame then add the menthol crystals.
- Step 10. Switch off the flame and allow cooling.
- Step 11.After cooling, you need to strain to remove excess turmeric paste.
- Step 12.Before transferring it to its respective container, put some lavender fragrance.
- Step 13.After that, it is now ready to use and apply into body, massage it and enjoy relaxation

C. BENEFITS:➤ *Turmeric Oil*

Getting a massage is one of the most relaxing experiences out there, especially when you have had a tough week and just need to unwind.

One of the major active compounds in turmeric is **curcumin**, a super-powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory.

- **Improves blood circulation.**When a massage is performed your muscles and body are twisted, patted and the different hand movements of the technician help stimulate the surface of your skin.
- **Increases flexibility.**
- **Improves your mood and can beat depression**
- **Beats body pain:** A massage feels perfect when you are aching all over. This is because if done properly it helps beat body pain.
- **Gets rid of dead skin and dirt effectively:** When you rub oil on your body or a technician does it for you, the oil helps get rid of dirt and dead skin especially in those areas that are prone to its buildup, especially places like your navel, behind the ears and knees. Not only does this help you stay clean and infection free but it also brightens up your skin and gets rid of any tanning.
- **Helps your nerves become healthier.** The nerves beneath your skin are stimulated and therefore help work better.
- **Improves heart health** .Points on your right palm and sole have the reflex centre of the heart. Applying gentle yet regular pressure on this point helps improve the functioning of your heart and stay healthy.
- **Keeps your skin healthy.**

- **Helps get rid of toxins Beats the symptoms of sinusitis and cold:** Massaging your face, nose and the area around your eyes helps relieve the symptoms of sinusitis and cold.
- **from the body:** During a massage since your blood circulation is improved it helps in the elimination of toxins from your body.

➤ *Coconut Oil*

According to history, coconut oil is a mystical elixir that may be used for a variety of purposes in both the kitchen and the bathroom. The internet provides a wealth of information about this tropical oil, cover topics like hair care, natural skin care, and recipes. According to the study made by A. Bautista, et al, 2022, Coconut have medicinal properties, and health benefits like, it can be an antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial and many more.

But with everything available, it might be difficult to distinguish between hype and reality. We can help you sort through the noise and discover the genuine advantages of coconut oil for skin.

- It moisturizes your skin, aids in reducing dryness, and enables moisture retention.
- It aids in protecting skin from pollution, dirt, and other environmental effects.
- It evens out the skin. Smoothing and softening the skin with coconut oil has a long-lasting positive impact on the texture of the skin.
- Nutty oil has a soothing, calming effect and can help diminish temporary redness when applied to skin. It also lowers temporary heat.
- It calms skin that is inflamed. You can get calming alleviation and discomfort relief with coconut oil.

There are several possible advantages of coconut oil for the skin. It may have anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antiviral activities, according to research. For dry skin, coconut oil is also incredibly moisturizing.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

As a result of study conducted by the researcher, it bring out the *Curcuma Longa - Turmeric Massage Essential Oil* was approved by the respondents in terms of looks, scent, texture and effect on their body pain, muscle pain and skin. The researchers believed that turmeric massage oil is an painkiller and anti-inflammatory. Being an painkiller and anti-inflammatory oil, turmeric is a best choice for massage oils intended specifically for aching muscles. The researcher suggests that this product, particularly for the College of Management and Business Technology, be added to NEUST's extension program. For all beneficiaries, this development has the potential to be a major source of earnings and business opportunities. It is strongly advised to do more research.

REFERENCES

- [1.] [https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-turmeric-\(Curcuma-longa-L.\)-essential-oil-Majdi-Mehrnia/83f5b7c096789745aabebb34e821887fa004379b](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effect-of-turmeric-(Curcuma-longa-L.)-essential-oil-Majdi-Mehrnia/83f5b7c096789745aabebb34e821887fa004379b)
- [2.] Turmeric Essential Oil Benefits <https://draxe.com/essential-oils/turmeric-essential-oil/>
- [3.] Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "turmeric". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 5 Dec. 2022, <https://www.britannica.com/plant/turmeric>
- [4.] KrisGunnars, BSc Medically reviewed by Kathy W. Warwick, R.D., CDE, Nutrition <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/top-10-evidence-based-health-benefits-of-turmeric>
- [5.] [https://momprepares.com/essential-oils/turmeric/Turmeric Essential Oil Uses](https://momprepares.com/essential-oils/turmeric/Turmeric-Essential-Oil-Uses)
- [6.] Fazila (B.Sc Biotech. & Bioinformatics) <https://www.turmericforhealth.com/general-info/what-is-turmeric-root-benefits-usage-dosage> Health benefits of Turmeric root
- [7.] Toden S, Theiss AL, Wang X, Goel A. Essential turmeric oils enhance anti-inflammatory efficacy of curcumin in dextran sulfate sodium-induced colitis <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28400554/>
- [8.] Anabrisa Ferreira Guimarães, Ana Cláudia Andrade Vinhasa, Angélica Ferraz Gomes,*, Luiz Humberto Souza and Patrícia Baier Krepskya ESSENTIAL OIL OF Curcuma longa https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341308946_ESSENTIAL_OIL_OF_Curcuma_longa
- [9.] Balakrishnan, K. V. In *Turmeric: The Genus Curcuma*, Ravisdran, P. N.; Babu, K. N.; Sivaraman, K., eds., CRC Press: Boca Raton, New York, London, 2007, cap. 8. https://books.google.com.ph/books/about/Turmeric.html?id=P2ykhQj6RvMC&redir_esc=y
- [10.] Sarker, S. D.* and Nahar, L. (2007) In "Turmeric: The Genus Curcuma" (editors: P. N. Ravindran, K. N. Babu and K. Sivaraman), Bioactivity of turmeric, CRC Press, USA.
- [11.] Alvin Gino M. Bautista; Joy N. Savellano; Jennalyn Y. Bautista. (Volume. 8 Issue. 2, February - 2023) "Production of Coconut-Neem-Moringa Essential Oil for Business Opportunities." , International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology (IJISRT), www.ijisrt.com. ISSN - 2456-2165 , PP :- 704-707. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7670821>